

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

FEATURES OF BULGARIA'S INNOVATION ACTIVITY (2019–2023)

Ivanova R.P.

Assoc. Professor, Ph.D.

University of Economics – Varna

Web of Science: Researcher ID JBJ-6290-2023

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9554-0349>

ABSTRACT

Innovation and the innovation activity of economic entities are of decisive importance for the level of development of every country and every region. The continuous shortening of product life cycles and the accelerated renewal of needs further reinforce the necessity of constant innovation. At the core of seeking and finding new ways, methods, and means of improving the competitive advantages of organizations lies in research and development (R&D), which is also the foundation of innovation. In this regard, at EU level, an expenditure benchmark has been set relative to the GDP of each country as well as the EU average.

The purpose of this article is to analyze the level of innovation and innovation activity of organizations in Bulgaria, as well as the country's position in regional and global rankings.

Keywords: innovation, innovation-active enterprises, R&D, Bulgaria.

INTRODUCTION

Innovation is an inseparable part of progress and the socio-economic growth of every country today. Focusing the attention of organizational leaders from all sectors of the economy on innovation and laying the foundation for stimulating its development is of primary importance for success at all levels – organizational, regional, national, and international.

Therefore, innovations and innovation processes are among the main factors subject to constant monitoring and analysis (V. Manolov, 2017, p. 51). They are also at the center of EU policies.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The term *innovation* today is part of the everyday vocabulary of individuals, private and public sector organizations, national governments, and supranational bodies such as the EU, EC, NATO, etc. There are numerous studies in the field of innovation, with the earliest reference dating back to the reign of King Edward VI, who used the term in 1548 to describe changes in nature or fashion as a new practice, method, etc. From a scientific standpoint, the modern meaning of the term was introduced by Joseph Schumpeter in 1934 (V. Manolov, 2016, p. 477). Later researchers provided their own interpretations, but the common element in all of them is *novelty*, which must be present regardless of the perspective. Today, we understand innovation as any new or improved product or service introduced on the market, a new or improved process, technology, organizational work method, or a new way of exploiting end products. Novelty can be considered from the perspective of organizations, markets, consumers, or the sector where it appears. The variety of interpretations of innovation has led to the use of different approaches in clarifying its essence – static, dynamic, and interactive (R. Ivanova, 2021, p. 12). Creating innovation presupposes the implementation of R&D, financial, production, and commercial activities, the entirety of which constitutes innovation activity. This activity has a complex and multifaceted character, encompassing a wide range of novelties (P. Vitlemov et al., 2014, p. 70).

At the heart of innovation lies human creativity and creative thinking, which are in direct connection with scientific knowledge and technological achievements in every field of activity. In turn, systematic work aimed at increasing knowledge and culture, as well as discovering new applications of already known knowledge, forms the essence of research and development (R&D) (nsi.bg). The existence of R&D enables innovation activity. However, investment in R&D alone does not ensure economic growth – it must be connected with concrete activities for implementing results in the real organizational transformation process. This is characterized by uncertainty and accompanied by the risk of failure, due to the impossibility of predicting outcomes with precision. For this reason, some researchers argue that generating new ideas and deriving real benefits from them depends on the ability of companies and their components to focus on transforming a new idea into an innovation (V. Manolov, 2016, p. 480). A key feature of innovation is its successful market realization.

The extent of innovation in organizations can be seen as both a result of changes in the economic environment and as a driver of significant changes within organizations themselves. This determines the level of innovation activity. Practice shows that organizations must accept the need for continuous generation of new ideas, as this ensures stronger competitive positions. It is also important to pay attention to new knowledge and to orient thinking not only toward satisfying existing needs, but also toward predicting future ones (V. Manolov, 2017, p. 52). In this respect, some researchers link innovation to the introduction of creative ideas into practice, leading to profit generation (Zhelev et al., 2014, p. 99).

The relevance of innovation activity is further highlighted by the specially developed strategies for each EU programming period – the Innovation Strategy for Smart Specialization (ISSS). The first ISSS for Bulgaria, developed for the 2014–2020 period, aimed to help the country transition from the group of “modest

(emerging) innovators” to the group of “moderate innovators.” The strategy focused on four priority areas: (1) Informatics and ICT, (2) Mechatronics and clean technologies, (3) Healthy lifestyle industries and biotechnology, (4) New technologies in creative and recreational industries.

The ISSS 2021–2027 builds on the results of the previous stage and reflects new EU policies in line with the opportunities and socio-economic challenges facing Bulgaria and other countries in the region. Analysis of the 2014–2020 period shows that unfortunately, Bulgaria did not achieve its ISSS goals in the field of innovation. The country remains faced with obstacles that prevent it from fully utilizing its potential and opportunities to improve its innovation performance above 70% of the EU average – the threshold for joining the “moderate innovators” group. It must be noted that in Bulgaria effective interaction between science, government, and business has not yet been achieved to create a functioning innovation ecosystem. Such an ecosystem would require synchronized policies enabling R&D development, providing a favorable basis for innovation.

Furthermore, ISSS 2021–2027 directs the attention of EU countries, including Bulgaria, to the implementation of the cohesion policy “*A Smarter Europe through innovation and support for economic transformation and modernization*” (ISSS 2021–2027, p. 6). For Bulgaria, five priority areas of development have been identified, reflecting the country’s competitive advantages and development capacity: (1) Informatics and ICT, (2) Mechatronics and microelectronics, (3) Healthy lifestyle industries, (4) New technologies in creative and recreational industries, (5) Clean technologies, circular and low-carbon economy. An important new feature compared to the previous programming period is the separate inclusion of mechatronics and mi-

croelectronics, driven by Bulgaria’s demonstrated potential in automation and robotics, intelligent manufacturing systems, artificial intelligence, and integrated circuit design and application. These areas underpin digitalization and smart transformation, which are key goals regionally and globally. In addition, there is a growing emphasis on the circular economy and sustainable development.

METHODOLOGY

To analyze the state of innovation activity and the degree of innovation performance in Bulgaria, officially published statistical data have been used from the National Statistical Institute (NSI), the Ministry of Innovation and Growth in Bulgaria, Innovation.bg, Eurostat, the European Innovation Scoreboard, and the Global Innovation Index. This ensures both easy access to information and the reliability of the data. The statistical data allow for greater precision in comparative analysis and in identifying trends in the examined field, which can then be visualized through charts. Given the time required for collecting, summarizing, and publishing data by NSI and Eurostat, the analyzed period is 2019–2023, which does not diminish the relevance of the conclusions drawn.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The implementation of innovation activity is closely linked to R&D and, respectively, to the funds invested in it. Reported data on expenditures as a share of GDP show that in Bulgaria there has been a decline during the 2019–2023 period (see Fig. 1). The level of these expenditures is significantly below the targets set in the country’s Innovation Strategies for Intelligent Specialization (ISSS), both for the previous and current programming periods. The planned R&D expenditure level in Bulgaria is 1.5% of GDP, while for the EU this target is 3%. The reason for this difference lies in the consideration of the specific economic conditions of each member state.

Fig. 1. Relative share of R&D expenditure in Bulgaria as a percentage of GDP (2017–2023)

As of 2023, the reported R&D expenditure in Bulgaria represents only half of the planned relative share compared to the country’s GDP.

The analysis of the absolute amount of funds invested in R&D in Bulgaria, broken down by enterprise size, shows growth – from BGN 673,122 in 2019 to BGN 943,747 in 2023. A continuous increase is observed only among large enterprises, while micro,

small, and medium-sized enterprises show fluctuations – periods of decline alternate with periods of growth. The lowest level of R&D expenditure among them was recorded in 2021. In the following two years, however, these enterprises also reported growth (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. R&D expenditure by enterprise size in Bulgaria (2019–2023)

The monitoring of state expenditures for R&D shows a steady increase in their absolute value for the period 2019–2024. By 2024, these expenditures are more than 1.8 times higher compared to 2019 (see Fig. 3). This can be regarded as a favorable trend, indicating an increased focus of the state on this sector.

Fig. 3. Dynamics of government R&D expenditure in Bulgaria (2019–2024)

From the perspective of funding sources, enterprise expenditures on R&D are the largest, followed by the public sector. Expenditures in the Higher Education sector are significantly lower, while those in the nonprofit sector can be considered negligible (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. R&D expenditure by funding sources and sectors in Bulgaria (2019–2023)

The degree of innovation development in a country is strongly influenced by the number of innovation-active enterprises, as a higher number implies a larger volume of innovations. This group includes enterprises that regularly engage in activities related to developing and introducing new or improved products, services, and processes during the reporting period. An important characteristic is that such enterprises do not have a specific organizational-legal form (N. Taneva,

D. Dimov 2007, p. 431). Therefore, this group includes diverse entities. In Bulgaria, the relative share of innovation-active enterprises for the period 2018–2022 shows an unfavorable trend, resulting in a lower share in 2022 compared to the beginning of the period. Structurally, from the perspective of economic activities, industry has consistently had more innovation-active enterprises compared to the services sector (see Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Share of innovation-active enterprises of total enterprises in Bulgaria by economic activity (2018–2022)

From the perspective of enterprise size, large enterprises (with more than 250 employees) account for over 70% of all innovation-active enterprises in each of the years in the reviewed period. This is a logical trend, as larger organizations have more opportunities and

free resources to allocate to R&D and innovation activities. At the same time, only about 1/5 of small enterprises (10–49 employees) fall into the innovation-active group (see Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Share of innovation-active enterprises of total enterprises in Bulgaria by enterprise size (2018–2022)

In recent years, cooperation among organizations in joint innovation projects—i.e., innovation collaboration—has become increasingly important. The analysis

of statistical data shows that the relative share of enterprises engaged in innovation cooperation in Bulgaria grew between 2018–2022, regardless of enterprise size or economic activity (see Fig. 7 and 8).

Fig. 7. Share of enterprises with innovation cooperation of total innovation-active enterprises in Bulgaria by enterprise size (2018–2022)

Fig. 8. Share of enterprises with innovation cooperation of total innovation-active enterprises in Bulgaria by economic activity (2018–2022)

At the same time, despite the growth, organizations engaged in innovation cooperation represent only about one-third of all innovation-active enterprises. This can be regarded as an unfavorable trend, requiring suitable corrective measures. One factor behind the lack of interest in developing innovation activity is the absence of proper legal frameworks to stimulate it, including the lack of an Innovation Act, special incentives, etc.

On the other hand, the level of innovation and innovation activity should not be considered only from a national perspective (K. Semova 2021, p. III-25). At the European level, the European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS) clearly shows Bulgaria's lag in innovation. In 2024, Bulgaria remains in 33rd place among EU and

neighboring countries, and second-to-last among EU member states (EIS 2024, p. 72). According to the Global Innovation Index 2024, Bulgaria ranks 38th among 133 countries (GII 2024, p. 18). Improvements were reported only in three areas: the level of employment in innovation-active enterprises; the relative share of foreign PhD students compared to the total number of PhD students in Bulgaria; and the expanding access to broadband internet, which plays a crucial role in digitalization (Innovation.bg 2024, p. 25).

In this context, it must be noted that the number of PhD students with Bulgarian citizenship is decreasing, while the number of foreign PhD students is increasing (see Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Dynamics of total PhD student enrollment in Bulgaria by academic year (2019–2025)

An increase in the second year compared to the beginning of the period is followed by a slight decline, and by the end of the period, there is a sharp drop in total PhD enrollments. The relative share of foreign students rises from 8.66% in the 2019/20 academic year to 10.84% in 2023/24, and 11.41% according to the data for 2024/25. This can be viewed positively in terms of growing foreign interest, but the declining participation of Bulgarian students is a negative trend. Furthermore, attention should be paid to the share of PhD students who successfully complete their studies. Data show that this share is relatively low (see Fig. 10). The reasons for this may vary, including the fact that the Higher Education Act in Bulgaria allows PhD students who meet

certain criteria to be deregistered with the right to defend within five years, while there is no mechanism obliging them to actually defend their dissertation, even for those studying under a state-funded position. The lack of sanctions, combined with the relatively high amount of the scholarship for full-time study during three years, serves as a good incentive for applicants to enroll in the academic degree “Doctor”. However, the low number of students who ultimately obtain a doctoral degree is problematic for the universities training them and negatively affects their accreditation evaluation by the National Evaluation and Accreditation Agency (NEAA) in Bulgaria.

Fig. 10. Dynamics of successfully defended PhD degrees in Bulgaria (2019–2024)

There is a clear downward trend in the number of students awarded PhD degrees during 2019–2024. A detailed analysis is needed to determine the reasons behind these results and to take appropriate measures.

The ICT sector in Bulgaria shows accelerated growth, with an increasing number of employees and rising exports of high-tech new products. However, the rising share of registered trademarks and industrial designs at the Patent Office indicates that Bulgaria’s competitive advantages lie more in low-tech intellectual property. Together with insufficient digitalization, de-

spite improved broadband access, this can be considered an unfavorable trend. More efforts are needed to stimulate the development of sectors where Bulgaria has potential for stronger regional and global positioning.

CONCLUSION

Innovation activity is among the key priorities of all EU member states. Strategies in this field take into account the current state of each economy and set targets to be achieved within the respective programming period. For Bulgaria, the main goal in the current ISSS is to transform the country into a “moderate innovator,”

although it continues to remain in the group of “emerging innovators.” Therefore, efforts by all stakeholders – state, business, NGOs, and educational institutions – must be intensified to generate enough new ideas and transform them into innovations of various types and applications, in order to adequately meet the expectations of the EC and the EU as a whole. Appropriate instruments must be developed to stimulate innovation, as well as stronger cooperation between the state, science, and business. The primary goal is both to support R&D implementation and to ensure broader access to innovations, enabling organizations to improve their performance and ensuring Bulgaria’s overall development in the field of innovation.

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